

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-ORIENTED COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF CADETS AS A PEDAGOGICAL FACTOR

Khatamova Gulbakhor

Researcher of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *This article focuses on technologies used in the field of pedagogy, general principles, general approaches to describing the rules of their construction, as well as the tasks facing the teacher in the development of career-oriented communicative competencies.*

Keywords: *professional-oriented communicative competencies, technology, design in technology, experimental training.*

In the development of profession-oriented communicative competence in a foreign language, it is aimed at implementing a limited range of private teaching tasks that not only reflect the uniqueness of one or another specialty, but also take into account the features of the content of training cadets for the profession.

Functions of developing profession-oriented communicative competence of cadets:

The development of communicative competence in the managerial function is used in the presence of recommendations on the organization of the educational process. Accordingly, in the development of exercises and tasks, the issue of planning the activities of cadets comes to the fore.

The communicative function does not ensure the gradual acquisition of communicative competence in a foreign language.

Information function. In addition to linguistic information, it has information related to foreign language science. In the development of profession-oriented communicative competences, the texts refer to the diligent selection and presentation of useful information by students from the point of view of the acquisition of professional competences..

Developmental learning function. The available information also creates a basis for the development and formation of students' worldview, development of career-oriented communicative competence.

The interdisciplinarity, functional nature of the development of profession-oriented communicative competences and its connection with the educational environment are becoming important for the population today.

The function of professional orientation consists in establishing a connection with the educational process and the profession of cadets and reflecting professional activity.

The function of self-control is that it is the basis for the rational organization of educational activities and the independent acquisition of knowledge and skills in the development of profession-oriented communicative competences of cadets.

The independent learning function provides students with an understanding of primary sources and the acquisition of skills for working with them.

In the development of profession-oriented communicative competence, it should be noted that, first of all, the activities of students are planned to ensure the most complete mastery of the selected teaching content at the stage of profession-oriented training. All the functions of

developing communicative competences described above allow the developer to understand and justify the planned results of his activity on creating a training manual according to the educational process.

In the development of profession-oriented communicative competence, it is first necessary to define the numerous concepts of "pedagogical technology" given in the scientific literature. The following definition is given in the encyclopedia of new philosophy: "Technology is a set of rules of raw materials, materials, intermediate products used in industry, acceptance, extraction, processing methods" [1].

The concept considered in a broad sense is transferred to the field of intellectual support, and considering it as a system of conditions, forms, methods, tools for the implementation of the task [2][3], pedagogical technology can be considered as a science that studies the most reasonable teaching methods. The principles, managers, methods, systems of forms of organizing the teaching process used in teaching within the framework of pedagogical technology are defined and based. In addition, pedagogical technology means the processes of scientific design of optimal teaching systems, educational processes, programs of educational subjects, educational modules, textbooks and training manuals.

Following L.P. Tarnayeva, the author considers educational technology in a broad sense as a complex integrative system that provides content, informational and procedural aspects, determining the pedagogical goal aimed at mastering knowledge, acquiring professional skills and forming personal qualities of students. [4]

In a narrow sense, the concept of technology is interpreted as a system of specially selected teaching methods according to the tasks facing teachers and students and located in a certain order.

In this work, we are talking about pedagogical technology in a broad sense, because in addition to the original teaching methods, the issues of determining the goals and tasks of teaching, developing the content of teaching, selecting teaching methods and tools are also considered..

When talking about the design of pedagogical processes, according to A.M. Novikov, it should be considered that the object of design within the framework of the development of pedagogical technology is very complex due to many factors that affect the final result [Novikov 2006]. Therefore, it is difficult to ensure that the design results exactly correspond to the developer's vision of the final product, which guarantees the achievement of educational goals. Nevertheless, according to O.Ye.Lomakina, the technological approach becomes important, because for the developer of this or that pedagogical object (educational process, educational-methodological support, etc.) "developing pedagogical objects" presents tools and methods that allow "building a logically consistent structure of output key symbols", the concepts of "technology" and "algorithm" are considered.

Using a technological approach, scientists seek to determine the systematic laws of the interaction of all the signs of the teaching process: students, teachers, teaching content, form, methods and tools, sources, and systematize the practical experience of designing various existing pedagogical objects [Zmeyov 2002; Kukushin 2003]. The technological approach to planning allows to predict the results with great accuracy and to control the pedagogical processes [Selevko 2006].

The technology of training foreign language cadets with career orientation is a set of methodical description that takes into account all the organizers of the educational process: students, teachers, the purpose, content, form, methods and tools of education.

According to A.R. Arutyunov, the modeling method is based on the theory of development of communicative competence of listeners [5]. The model is characterized by simulating the functions of a real object, showing the most important connections and relationships as an additional object in pedagogical research [2]. Thus, the modeling method is taken as a goal in the development of communicative competence of cadets.

In this case, the actual design process may differ from the model.

The rules described in a number of works related to the principles of technology development [5] allow defining the main requirements for the methods of developing the communicative competence of listeners.

First of all, the connection between the theory and practice of design in technology is important, the clear description of the methodological foundations of the development of the communicative competence of the listeners is observed by recommendations for their implementation.

Secondly, the technology should not have a strict instructional nature and should allow for the possibility of integration of various contradictions in relation to the scientific concept that formed its basis, the possibility of checking the results of its practical application.

In order to fulfill this requirement, the technology should provide mechanisms that allow the effective development of communicative competence with its help.

Then an important characteristic of technology is its objectivity.

The use of technologies by various pedagogues who develop training manuals should lead to the planned result.

It is given in the form of methodological descriptions planned for the development of communicative competences, one of the sections of this research is dedicated to their description.

In our opinion, the presence of feedback is important, that is, there are opportunities to control and correct the results of the development of communicative competence at each stage, which allows to reduce the risk of identifying significant inconsistencies in the characteristics of the planned experimental training results. Achieving the goal through definitions is an essential condition that allows the teacher to perform self-examination and make necessary adjustments..

Considering the issues of development of pedagogical technologies, A.M. Novikov notes that in the field of pedagogy there are no general approaches to the definition of technologies, general principles, rules of their construction. The application of one or another principle is determined by the specific content of each project [2]. Therefore, in the development of profession-oriented communicative competence, it is necessary to determine the nature of the tasks facing the teacher and the categories and concepts used to describe the scientific basis of the improved new methods.

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